

P: ISSN No. 2321-290X
E: ISSN No. 2349-980X

RNI No. UPBIL/2013/55327

VOL.- XII , ISSUE- IX June - 2025

Shrinkhla Ek Shodhparak Vaicharik Patrika

Analysis of Techno Stress among Higher Education Students

Paper Id : 20347 Submission Date : 2025-06-07 Acceptance Date : 2025-06-21 Publication Date : 2025-06-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16323331

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/shinkhlala.php#8>

Diksha Singh

M.Ed.
Department Of Education
University Of Allahabad
Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Saroj Yadav

Associate Professor
Department Of Education
University Of Allahabad
Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

Technology is now a crucial part of our society and as educational systems are pressured to integrate new technologies, teachers' ability to adapt to these changes and innovations has become essential for success. This integration of technology into the classroom and the adaptation to various technological methods of education is commonly referred to as E-Learning in simple terms .E Learning, regardless of the terminology used, remains essentially the same. Despite widespread discussion, there is no standardized definition or common terminology. The situation mirrors the semantic debates of 1970s concerning computers and their applications to education, where various phases, such as computer (aided, assisted, based, managed, enabled) (instruction, learning, education, training) were used interchangeable without significant difference. (Rusby,2001).

Keywords Techno Stress , Higher Education Students.

Introduction

E-Learning can be described as the use of digital technologies and media to facilitate, support, and improve teaching, learning, assessment, and evaluation. (Armitage and O'Leary,2003).

The American Society for Training and Development, under the bracket ASTD, defines E-Learning as teaching and learning that is delivered, facilitated, or mediated through electronic technology, specifically for the purpose of education. (Rossen and Hartely,2001).

Meaning of Techno stress

Techno stress as described in the literature is a syndrome characterized by three main dimensions: a negative attitude towards information and communication technology (evaluative dimension), high level of computer anxiety (emotional dimension), Self-efficacy with ICT (cognitive dimension). Individuals experiencing technostress generally have a negative overall view of computers, their functions and their societal effects, leading them to avoid discussing or engaging with technology and resisting technological changes. Rosen and Weil (1990), Brosan(1998).

Research questions

1. Is there any difference in the level of techno-stress among higher education students on the basis of gender?
2. Is there any difference in the level of techno-stress among higher education students on the basis of professional and non-professional courses?
3. Is there any difference in the level of techno-stress among students of undergraduate and postgraduate courses?

Objective of study

1. To compare the level of techno stress among male and female higher education students.

2. To compare the level of techno stress among students enrolled in undergraduate and postgraduate courses.
3. To compare the level of techno stress among students enrolled in professional and non-professional courses.

Review of Literature

Abdullah et al.(2023) explored how problematic internet use (PIU) links internet use to technostress and how personality traits influence PIU among university students in Pakistan. Data from 165 students was analyzed using Smart PLS. PIU partially explained the connection between internet use and technostress. Conscientiousness reduced PIU, while neuroticism increased it. Universities should provide workshops and counseling to help students manage internet use and reduce technostress. Sharma & Gupta,(2023) studied on Investing the role of technostress, cognitive appraisal, and coping strategies on student's learning performance in higher education : A multidimensional transactional theory of stress approach. The investigator found that The COVID-19 pandemic has hastened the shift to technology-enhanced learning (TEL) in education. Silva, Sousa & Moniz (2022) did a study on Technostress among higher education students during the COVID-19 outbreak. The researcher investigated that Higher education students' interactions with technology in learning environments can lead to feelings of stress and anxiety.

Torales et al.(2022) conducted study on Technostress, anxiety, and depression among university students. This study indicates that increased technology use among university students, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, has led to significant levels of technostress, anxiety, and depression. A survey of 378 Paraguayan students found that 47.4% reported low to moderate technostress, while 5.2% experienced severe levels. Additionally, 58.5% met criteria for generalized anxiety, and 60.3% exhibited significant depressive symptoms. Notably, technostress was significantly associated with both anxiety and depression. Abbas, Saud, Ekowati, Usm and & Setia (2020) conducted a study on technology and stress - a proposed framework for coping with stress in Indonesian higher education. The researcher investigated that Technology has become a vital part of daily communication, with its use extending across both personal and professional spheres and impacting nearly every aspect of life, including education.

Methodology

Research Methodology-

Researcher had employed a descriptive survey research for conducting the present study. To find and collect data various methods have been used (questionnaire, survey, and self-made tools).

Population and sample-

The current study focuses on higher education students enrolled for undergraduate and postgraduate in both general and professional courses of University of Allahabad, Prayagraj. The present study will contain 150-200 students as sample.

Variables -

1. Techno stress
2. Higher education students

Analysis

Process of Data Collection

The data for the current study has been collected from student of undergraduate and post graduate program of professional and non-professional course of students of University of Allahabad.

Ho(1)-There is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between male and female higher education students.

Table-1- t-test comparing level of techno stress between male and female higher education students.

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error	t-ratio	Significance
Male	80	33.90	3.919	.438	1.804	Not significant
Female	70	35.00	3.493	.418		

*at 0.05 level

Interpretation- As noticed in above table, the calculated value of t-test i.e. 1.818 is less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance, "There is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between male and female higher education students" is accepted. The mean score of female higher education students i.e. 35.00 which is greater than male higher education students which shows that female higher education students experience more techno stress than male students.

H₀(2) : There is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between undergraduate and postgraduate students.

Table-2- t-test for comparing level of techno stress between undergraduate and postgraduate students.

Stream	N	Mean	S.D.	Std Er.	t-ratio	Sig.
Undergraduate	75	34.31	3.472	.401	.347	Not Significant
Postgraduate	75	34.52	4.038	.466		

*at 0.05 level

Interpretation- As noticed in the above table, the calculated value of t-test i.e. .347 is less than the table value 1.96, at 0.05 level of significance, therefore nul hypothesis "there is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between undergraduate and postgraduate students." is accepted.

The mean score of postgraduate students is 34.52 which is greater than mean score of undergraduate students i.e. 34.31, which shows that postgraduate students experience more techno stress than undergraduate students.

H₀ (3): There is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between students enrolled in professional and non-professional courses.

Table -3 t-test for comparing level of techno stress between students Enrolled in professional and non-professional courses.

Course type	N	Mean	S.D.	Std Error	t ratio	Significance
Professional	70	34.16	3.472	.437	.783	Not Significant
Non professional	80	34.64	4.038	.430		

*At 0.05 level

Interpretation- As noticed in the above table, the calculated value of T test is less than the table value 1.96, at 0.05 level of significance, therefore nul hypothesis "there is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between students enrolled in professional and non-professional courses" is accepted. The mean score of students of non professional courses is 34.64 which is greater than mean score of students professional courses i.e. 34.16 which shows that students of nonprofessional courses experience more techno stress than students of professional courses.

Educational Implications

The findings of this study, which suggest no significant difference in techno stress levels across gender, academic level, and course type, indicate that techno stress is a universal concern among higher education students. Consequently, stakeholders in the educational process including teachers, students, curriculum developers, and classroom practitioners , must actively engage in strategies to mitigate its impact.

Implications for Teachers

Awareness and Sensitization: Teachers must be made aware of the phenomenon of techno stress and its potential impact on student engagement, motivation, and academic performance.

Flexible Teaching Approaches: Teachers should incorporate a blend of digital and non digital teaching methods to avoid overexposure to technology.

Emotional Support: Teachers should create a supportive classroom environment where students feel comfortable discussing the challenges they face due to digital demands.

Professional Development: Regular training and workshops should be organized for teachers to help them develop strategies to minimize students' digital fatigue and techno stress.

Assignment Planning: Teachers should design assignments and learning tasks considering the cognitive load and screen time already demanded by other courses.

Implications for Students

Self-awareness and Self-regulation: Students should be guided to recognize signs of techno stress and adopt self-regulation strategies such as scheduled technology breaks, time management, and prioritization of tasks.

Digital Literacy and Coping Skills: Training programs for students must not only focus on technical skills but also include modules on coping with digital stress and maintaining a healthy technology-life balance.

Promoting Help-seeking Behavior: Students should be encouraged to seek academic and emotional support when experiencing techno stress, thereby reducing stigma around mental health concerns linked to technology use.

Participative Learning: Students should actively engage in participatory learning techniques that reduce passive screen exposure and foster collaboration and interaction.

Implications for Curriculum Developers-

Curriculum Redesign: Curricula must be restructured to include aspects of digital wellness and techno stress management as integral components.

Balanced Technology Integration: Curriculum planners should advocate for the judicious use of technology in teaching-learning processes, avoiding excessive digital dependency.

Skill Development Modules: Include specific modules focusing on stress management, mindfulness practices, and digital etiquette as part of the core curriculum.

Assessment Methods: Alternative assessment strategies that do not heavily rely on continuous online submissions should be considered to reduce techno stress.

Implications for Classroom Transaction Strategies-

Blended Learning Models: Employ a hybrid model that integrates face-to-face interaction with digital learning, maintaining a healthy balance between technology use and traditional methods.

Interactive and Engaging Activities: Incorporate active learning strategies such as group discussions, role plays, case studies, and peer-teaching that promote cognitive engagement without digital overload.

Scheduled Digital Breaks: Intentionally plan breaks during long online sessions or technology-heavy classes to prevent digital fatigue.

P: ISSN No. 2321-290X

RNI No. UPBIL/2013/55327

VOL.- XII , ISSUE- IX June - 2025

E: ISSN No. 2349-980X

Shrinkhla Ek Shodhparak Vaicharik Patrika

Mindful Use of Educational Technology: Use technology tools purposefully only where they add value to the learning experience rather than as a default mode of delivery.

Personalized Learning Paths: Offer students flexibility and choices in how they engage with learning resources, acknowledging that different students might have varying tolerances to technology use.

Result and Discussion

Findings Related to Gender Differences in Techno stress

The analysis revealed that there is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between male and female higher education students. The mean techno stress scores for male and female students were (33.9 and 35.5), and the t-test result ($t = 1.818$, $p > 0.05$) indicates that the difference is not statistically significant.

This suggests that both male and female students experience comparable levels of techno stress despite possible differences in their technological exposure or preferences. It indicates that techno stress is a universal experience among students, irrespective of gender.

Findings Related to Academic Level (Undergraduate and Postgraduate)

Similarly, the study found no significant difference in the level of techno stress between undergraduate and postgraduate students. The average techno stress levels for undergraduates and postgraduates were (34.31 and 34.52), with a t-test result of ($t = .347$, $p > 0.05$), showing no statistically significant difference.

This indicates that academic level does not substantially influence students' experience of techno stress. Both groups may be equally affected due to the increasing integration of technology across all academic levels.

Findings Related to Course Type (Professional and Non-professional)

Finally, the data indicated no significant difference in the level of techno stress between students enrolled in professional and non-professional courses. The mean techno stress scores for students in professional and non-professional programs were (34.16 and

34.64), with a t-test result ($t = .783$, $p > 0.05$).

This finding suggests that the nature of the course (whether professional or nonprofessional) does not significantly affect how students experience techno stress. The pervasive use of digital tools across all disciplines may explain this uniformity in stress levels.

Findings

There is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between male and female higher education students.

There is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between undergraduate and postgraduate students.

There is no significant difference in the level of techno stress between students enrolled in professional and non-professional courses

Conclusion

Technostress, the stress caused by using technology, is a growing issue among higher education students. Research highlights its main causes, such as excessive technology use, complexity, and constant connectivity, which negatively impact students' academic performance and well-being. While studies suggest solutions like digital literacy training and stress management programs, they often focus on general student populations, leaving gaps in understanding how differently-abled students are affected. Additionally, there is limited research on how advanced technologies, like meta-technology, can help reduce technostress. This study aims to address these gaps by exploring technostress among students and the role of technology in higher education. that technostress is a universal concern among higher education students. Consequently, stakeholders in the educational process including teachers, students, curriculum developers, and classroom practitioners must actively engage in strategies to mitigate its impact.

References

1. Asad, M. M., Erum, D., Churi, P., & Moreno Guerrero, A. J. (2023). Effect of technostress on psychological well-being of post-graduate students: A perspective and correlational study of higher education management. *International Journal of Information Management, DataInsights*, 3(1), 100149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijime.2022.100149>
2. Armitage, S., & O'Leary, R. (2003). *A guide for learning technologists (LSTN E learning Series No.4)*. York: LTSN. In Sharma, R.C. & Mishra, S. (2007). *Cases on*

- Global E-learning Practices: Successes & Pitfalls*. London: Information Science Publishing.
3. Brosnan, M. J. (1998). *Technophobia. The psychological impact of Information Technology*. London: Routledge. In Agut, S., Grau, R. & Salanova, M. (2001). *Technostress and Burnout among Spanish Workers: Gender differences*. In C. Wilkert, E. Torkelson & J. Pryce (Eds.), *Occupational Health Psychology: Europe 2001*, Nottingham: I-WHO Publications, 28-31.
 4. French, D., Hale, C., Johnson, C., & Farr, G. (Eds). (1999). *Internet-Based learning: An introduction & framework for higher education & business*. London: Kogan Page. In Sharma, R.C. & Mishra, S. (2007). *Cases on Global E-learning Practices: Successes & Pitfalls*. London : Information Science Publishing.
 5. Khan, B.H. (1997). *Web-Based instruction: What it is & why is it?* In B.H. Khan (Ed), *Web-Based instruction (5-18)*. Englewood Cliff, NJ: Educational Technology. In Sharma, R.C. & Mishra, S. (2007). *Cases on Global E-learning Practices: Successes & Pitfalls*. London : Information Science Publishing.
 6. Komala, H. M., & Meena, P. T. (2017). *Techno Stress-A New Bane to the Students*. *International Journal of Informative & Futuristic Research*, 4(5), 6125-6129.
 7. Makrakis, V. (1993). *Gender & computing in schools in Japan: the "We can, I can't Paradox*. *Computer Education*, 20(2), 191-198.
 8. McIlroy, B., Tierney, M., & Gordon, M. (2001). *The relation of gender & background Experience to self-reported computing anxieties & cognitions*. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 77(1), 21-33.
 9. Mishra, S. (2001). *Designing online learning, COL knowledge series*. Vancouver : Commonwealth of Learning. In Sharma, R.C. & Mishra, S. (2007). *Cases on Global E-learning Practices: Successes & Pitfalls*. London : Information Science Publishing.
 10. Mohan, K. P. (2004). *Work Specific Locus of Control as a Moderator of the Relationship Between Organizational Stressors & Job Related Well Being (Unpublished doctoral dissertation)*. Srinakharinwirot University: Srinakharinwirot, 3.
 11. Nimrod, G. (2017). *Technostress: Measuring a new threat to well-being in later life*. *Aging & Mental Health*, 22(8), 1086–1093. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2017.1334037>
 12. Ogletree, S. M., & Williams, S. W. (1990). *Sex & sex-typing effects on computer Attitudes & aptitude*. *Sex Roles*, 23(11/12), 703-712.
 13. Rushby, N. (2001). *Editorial*. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 32(5), 509-511. In Sharma, R.C. & Mishra, S. (2007). *Cases on Global E-Learning Practices: Successes & Pitfalls*. London : Information Science Publishing.
 14. Rosen, E., & Hartley, D. (2001). *Basics of e-learning*. Info-line, 109. In Sharma, R.C. & Mishra, S. (2007). *Cases on Global E-Learning Practices: Successes & Pitfalls*. London Information Science Publishing.
 15. Rosen, L. D., & Weil, M. M. (1990). *Computers, classroom instruction & the Computerphobic university student*. *Collegiate Microcomputer*, 5(4), 257-283.
 16. Sharma, S., & Gupta, B. (2023). *Investigating the role of technostress, cognitive appraisal, and coping strategies on students' learning performance in higher education: A multidimensional transactional theory of stress approach*. *Information Technology & People*, 36 (2), 626-660. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-06-2021-0505>
 17. Silva, O., Sousa, Á., & Moniz, A. I. D. d. S. A. (2022). *Technostress among higher education students during the COVID-19 outbreak*. *International Journal of Online Pedagogy and Course Design*, 12(2), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijopcd.305726>
 18. Tarafdar, M., Tu, Q., Ragu-Nathan, B. S., & Ragu-Nathan, T. S. (2007). *The Impact of Technostress on Role Stress and Productivity*. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 24(1), 301–328. <https://doi.org/10.2753/MIS0742-122240109>
 19. Torales, J., Torres-Romero, A. D., Di Giuseppe, M. F., & et al. (2022). *Technostress, anxiety, and depression among university students: A report from Paraguay*. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 68(5), 1063-1070. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207640221099416>
 20. Upadhyaya, P., Vrinda Impact of technostress on academic productivity of university students. *EduInfTechnol* 26, 1647–1664 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10319-9>
 21. Vyas, M. (2023). *Traditional learning students' insights*. *PNR*, 13, 3986–3995. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S07.502>
 22. Wang, X., Tan, S. C., & Li, L. (2020). *Measuring university students' technostress in technology-enhanced learning: Scale development and validation*. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 36(4), 96–112. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.5329>
 23. White, G. (2003). *E-learning-key Australian initiatives (An opportunity for all Learners)*. In Khirwadkar, A. (2008). *Integrating Multimedia Package at Pre Service Level: A Technopedagogy for Smart Schools*. *Indian journal of open Learning*, 7 7(1), 25-33.
 24. Zhao, G., Wang, Q., Wu, L., & Zhang, M. (2022). *Exploring the structural relationship between university support, students' technostress, and burnout in*

P: ISSN No. 2321-290X

RNI No. UPBIL/2013/55327

VOL.- XII , ISSUE- IX June - 2025

E: ISSN No. 2349-980X

Shrinkhla Ek Shodhparak Vaicharik Patrika

technology-enhanced learning.Asia-Pacific Education Research, 31(4), 463–473. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-02100588-4>